

CHARACTERISTICS OF MORAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS THROUGH AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article focuses on moral education of students through an innovative approach and its specific features and creative technologies for improving the processes of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities. he talks about developing mechanisms, paying great attention to the development of practical competence.*

Keywords: *innovation, creative technology, models, riskological and prognostic competencies, integrative approach, subject-subject relations.*

In the introduction of the article, while we focus on the specific features of providing moral education to elementary school students through an innovative approach in today's new educational system of Uzbekistan, great importance is attached to the wide implementation of creative technologies for improving the processes of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities, and the development of promising models of innovative potential development.

In the prospective plan of the United Nations Organization for Education, Science and Culture called "UNESCO: Horizons of 2020" aimed at the globalization of education, effective organization of educational processes aimed at the formation of moral education and personal and professional qualities of primary school students through an innovative approach and systematic work on the implementation of practical projects to improve the quality and competitiveness of personnel training is being carried out today. Especially in the conditions of digitization of education, improvement of didactic mechanisms of development of practical, riskological and prognostic competencies of pedagogues is becoming an important priority. A number of scientific researches are being carried out on the design of teaching technologies aimed at imparting moral education to elementary school students through an innovative approach, the development of didactic systems for organizing effective collaborative activities in an innovative educational environment, and the improvement of preventive mechanisms for preventing psychological and pedagogical obstacles that arise in innovative processes. At the same time, expanding the global innovative-integrative educational environment by integrating advanced foreign experiences, improving the mechanism of optimizing the dynamics of innovative-professional growth based on the acmeological approach is of great importance. In our republic, great attention is being paid to improving the content and quality of higher education, developing mechanisms for providing moral education to primary school students through an innovative approach, and developing the practical competence of future primary school teachers in pedagogical higher education institutions as a priority for the development of school education. "Increasing the quality of training of highly qualified personnel for the modernization of the country, sustainable socio-economic development, development of human capital based on the requirements of the labor market, increasing the level of coverage with higher education, highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking, able to make independent decisions based on international standards" creating the necessary conditions for the training of personnel, the manifestation of their intellectual

abilities and formation as a spiritually mature person"¹ are defined as the priority directions of the development of the higher education system.

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However, in the conditions of digitization of education, the development of the content, didactic parameters, interactive form, methods and tools of improving the processes of preparation for the activity of teaching moral education to elementary school students through an innovative approach on the basis of an integrative approach is particularly relevant.

In providing moral education to elementary school students through an innovative approach, it is necessary to justify the fact that the preparation of teachers for innovative-pedagogical activity is a socio-pedagogical problem, the pedagogical-psychological features of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activity, and the essence of the integrative approach.

Based on the modeling of the innovative activity of the teacher, the content and types of innovative-pedagogical activity, the content of the basic skills and qualifications necessary for the teacher in the implementation of innovative-pedagogical activity are shown, the important professional and personal characteristics and qualities of the teacher-innovator are described. Also, the importance and necessity of the concept of "innovation in education" in the effective organization and management of innovative processes in general secondary educational institutions, taking into account its specific features, new developments, educational and educational technologies, and the introduction of innovations will be highlighted.

In the article, innovative-pedagogical activity is interpreted as a product of goal-oriented actions carried out by the pedagogical team, creativity, inquisitiveness, knowledge, sociability, innovative activity, initiative and regular work on oneself and professional-motivational orientation to creativity and solving collective problems. . Innovative activity means a sequence of certain stages (motivational, cognitive, integrative, reflexive) characterized by positive professional quality changes. This activity requires the ability to deviate from the norm that represents the recognized standard in specific socio-economic conditions, internal adaptation to new requirements, and the ability to overcome psychological barriers. This aspect of innovative activity involves providing a set of tools necessary for professional development, consciously changing the pedagogical reality. In this case, relying on an integrative approach will lead to an effective result. When implementing an integrative approach, it is important to consciously and systematically analyze the issue, analyzing all the main components and the necessary internal and external relations from the point of view of achieving the goal. It is explained in "Pedagogy" that the integrative approach is a concept that means the joint application of several approaches (situational, systematic, innovative, etc.) to the managed object in the organization and management of the educational process. Also, the concept of integration is "integrity, systematicity, interdependence, complexity" in many literatures; "principle, process and result"; "combining scattered parts into a whole"; described in terms of "synthesized courses and interdisciplinary connections". Within the framework of the study, the block matrix proposed by

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" // National database of legal documents, 09.10.2019, No. 06/19/5847/3887 ; 04/30/2020, No. 06/20/5987/0521

scientists was used as a basis for clarifying the content, structure and components of preparing future teachers for innovative activities. It is the block matrix that has a rapid effect on the development of innovative pedagogical activity in them by expanding the integrative content of the training of future teachers for professional activity.

Another important aspect of the block matrix of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activity is that it serves as a mechanism of integration of practical training for professional activity with realized and unrealized potential. It is the integrativeness between blocks of the educational process that allows to reveal the potential of a person, realized as innovative knowledge, skills, experience, and unrealized as motivation, innovative thinking and virtual innovative experience. Preparation of future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activity from the point of view of integration as a whole pedagogical system, all links of the educational process: academic subjects, special courses and seminars, optional trainings, scientific-research works, activities outside the auditorium, socially useful work, educational and pedagogical practice, includes independent and project education. The set of matrices has a unique "building" appearance, and its internal logic reflects the entire process of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities. This is an important feature of the block matrix that is, based on vertical and horizontal directions (psychological-pedagogical knowledge), as a result, a new integrative "plane" - innovative training of future teachers develops. "Improving the processes of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities based on an integrative approach" describes the state of preparation of future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities, the practice of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities based on credit-module technology in pedagogical higher education institutions. Based on the analysis of the state education standard, the qualification requirements of the bachelor's course, the curriculum and science programs, it is noticeable that the systematization of the general pedagogical content of preparing future teachers for innovative activities has not been sufficiently studied.

A special training course on the development of a subjective point of view in the process of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities ("Fundamentals of innovative-pedagogical activities of future teachers") includes four independent modules:

1. The subject of pedagogical communication.
2. Subject-subject relationship skills.
3. Technology of organizing collective creative activity.

4. I am the subject of innovative-pedagogical activity. The "Pedagogical subject of communication" module of the special training course includes four stages and is aimed at creating motivation in participants, creating a psychological environment based on game techniques, analyzing concepts related to subject-subject relations in the process of communication, self-analysis and evaluation.

The module of the special training course "Technology of organizing collective creative activity" included forms of teamwork (discussion, role-playing, business games, project-based team activity) for group discussion of situations. In the module "I am the subject of innovative-pedagogical activity", special attention was paid to group mini-projects, business games imitating educational activities at school, problem situations, and retrospective reflection aimed at focusing on the results of one's own activities.

Acquiring knowledge that enriches innovative activity Content of activities aimed at improving the processes of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activity

Analyzing the nature of processes and situations focused on innovative-pedagogical activity. Formation of personal and professional qualities reflecting the skills of innovative - pedagogical activity Active participation in the processes of innovative - pedagogical activity Factors for improving the processes of preparation for innovative - pedagogical activity Subjects influencing the formation of innovative - pedagogical activity Professionally important personal and professional qualities and characteristics of the future teacher for innovative pedagogical activity social-humanitarian, psychological-pedagogical, natural-scientific, professional-personal features of training Effective use of advanced methods and methods of transfer of innovative experience Motivational approach to training for innovative-pedagogical activity Mechanisms of training for innovative-pedagogical activity Study of future teachers' inclination to innovations and their abilities, development of interests selection of adequate methodical methods and tools for the use of innovative technologies aimed at learning advanced practice reflexive approach to the processes of preparation for innovative activities It is noticeable that the collaborative organization of the processes of preparation for innovative-pedagogical activities has given good results.

In conclusion, it can be said that the following conclusions were made regarding the improvement of the processes of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities based on an integrative approach. 1. Innovative-pedagogical activity - is carried out on the basis of goal-oriented actions of individual teachers and pedagogical team, creativity, curiosity, knowledge, communication, innovative activity, initiative and professional-motivational orientation to self-regular work and creativity.

2. In clarifying the content, structure and components of preparation of future teachers for innovative activities, it is appropriate to base on the block matrix.

3. Preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activity, psychological-pedagogical training, mastering social-humanitarian and natural-scientific sciences, an important aspect of the block-matrix that creates the ability to implement methodical, special and innovative activities is its integration of practical training for professional activity with realized and unrealized potential is to serve as a mechanism.

4. The model of improving the processes of preparing future teachers for innovative-pedagogical activities based on an integrative approach, the use of purposeful, meaningful, process, organizational and result blocks guarantees the achievement of the expected results.

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